

PULTRUSION SYSTEM FOR CONTINUOUS FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE WITH BRAIDING TECHNIQUE

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1. Introduction

Pultrusion is one of the most common method for continuous fabrication of fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) with uniform cross section. In general, during the pultrusion process, unidirectional fibers are impregnated with low viscosity thermosetting resins before passing through a series of dies for shaping and curing. This provides the composite with a preferential load bearing capacity mostly in the longitudinal direction while this capacity reduces significantly in other loading directions. Additionally, the usage of thermosetting resin impedes the possibility of recycling. Therefore, to solve these problems, a combination of pultrusion and braiding technologies to produce continuous fiber reinforced thermoplastic composites was proposed.

Due to the high viscosity of thermoplastic resins, impregnation of the resin into the reinforcement fibers is difficult. In this study, the intermediate material was used for pultrusion process. Carbon fibers were used as the reinforcement while the PA66 resin fiber bundle was used as the matrix resin. These fibers made into commingled yarns and used as the intermediate material. Commingled yarn is good impregnation state. Commingled yarn offer a potential for low cost manufacturing, due to reduced impregnation times and applied pressure during processing. Additionally, the ratio of reinforced fiber into intermediate material can be select. Therefore, intermediate material on the many conditions can be designed..

The purpose of this study is to investigate the pultrusion conditions of the beams using braided performs with thermoplastic resin. Forces onThe pultrusion conditions is filling ratio and resin

viscosity, die temperature. To measure the temperature evolution of the material during pultrusion, thermocouples were inserted into braided fabrics. Cross-sectional observation and tensile test were performed for the pultruded composites. From these results, the effect of molding conditions on the consolidation state and the mechanical properties was discussed.

2. Effect of filling ratio

3.1 Materials

Carbon fibers (UTS50-12000 F22 800tex, Toho Tenax) were used as the reinforcement while the PA66 resin fiber (L-235T35B Nylon66 235dtex, melting temperature: 265 °C) were used as the matrix resin. Carbon fibers (UTS50 12000 filaments) and PA66 (L-235T35B) were combined in a parallel hybrid yarn arrangement and used as the BYs and MEYs and CYs. Tubular braided fabric was fabricated with 48 BYs and 24 MEYs. To keep constant the volume fraction of carbon fibers in the composites (V_f), V_{fi} and number of CYs were changed. Three type of V_{fi} were prepared. Three type of number of CYs were prepared. The braiding angle is 55 degree, and V_f is 50%. All of specification of tubular braided fabrics is shown TABLE.1.

Braided fabrics was flattened and pulled into the pultrusion die having an L-shape hole. During the passage into the die, the resin fibers of the braided fabric melted and flowed into reinforcing fibers. The result was two-layer braided composites beams with L-shaped cross section. Additionally, CYs were placed inside the braid along the braid axis.

TABLE I. TYPE OF SPECIMENS

Sample name	Filling ratio (%)	Number of CYs	Vfi	Molding speed(mm/min)
No.1	100	79	49.2	22
No.2	110	77	44.7	22
No.3	120	73	40.9	22

3.2. Pultrusion System

The pultrusion line is shown in Figure 1. The braided fabrics were made horizontally by a braiding machine. A preheating die and a molding die were prepared for the forming of the L-shaped beam. The braided fabrics were pre-heated in the preheating die up to near melting temperature (255 °C) of the resin fiber for easier impregnation. The molding die had the L-shaped molding hole with a 30 mm side and a 3 mm thickness. The length of the molding die was 470 mm, which was separated into six heating zones. The temperature at each sections of the molding die was set respectively at 290, 290, 290, 280, 270, 260 °C from the entrance side. The pultruded beam was pulled out by pulling system. The pulling system is composed of six motor driven rollers that compressed and pulled the pultruded beams. The pultruded beam was cooled by compressed air at the exit of molding die.

Figure 1. Pultrusion line and structure of die

3.3 RESULT AND DISCUSSION

3.3.1 Temperature history

The thermal evolution inside the beam during pultrusion is shown in Figure 2. General molding time is decided by the relationship between length of molding die and the molding speed. When the molding speed was increased, the point that internal temperature of braided fabrics achieved 290 degree shifted away from the entrance to exit of molding, So, the resin does not achieve melting point at entrance of the molding die. In this study, the essential molding time was calculated from molding speed and actual molding distance. The actual

molding distance was defined as distance from the point that internal temperature of braided fabrics reached 290 °C to exit of taper zone where pressure was applied to braided fabrics. The value of the molding distance divided by the molding speed was defined as the essential molding time. The molding distance decreased at higher molding speed, so that the essential molding time was decreased compared with essential molding time estimated by the molding speed.

The essential molding time are shown in Table II. Relationships between the essential molding time and filling ratio are shown in Figure 3. When the filling ratio was increased, the essential molding time decreased. As a result, the point that internal temperature of braided fabrics achieved molding temperature shifted away from the entrance to exit of molding, due to incomplete heating up inside the molding. It was considered that the heat transmission was slow due to the increased amount of reinforcement and matrix in the die.

Point where temperature reached maximum temperature 290 degrees of die

Figure 2. Temperature history

Figure 3. Relationships between essential molding time and filling ratio

Although molding speed was same, essential molding time was changed. Thermal capacity of each materials were focused on. If matrix increased, thermal capacity is decreased.

3.3.2 Cross sectional observation

The cross sectional photographs of specimen are shown in Figure 4. The dark regions indicate un-impregnation area. The un-impregnation area increased with increasing the filling ratio. The un-impregnation areas of specimens are shown in TABLE II. The reason is considered that thermal conductivity was decreased and the essential time was decreased

Relationships between un-impregnation area and molding time are shown Figure 5. The un-impregnation area decreased with increasing the essential molding time.

Figure 4. Cross section of specimen

Figure 5. Relationships between the un-impregnation area and essential molding time

TABLE II. TYPE OF SPECIMENS

Sample name	No.1	No.2	No.3
Essential Molding time(min)	4.53	3.23	2.76
Un-impregnation area(%)	15.5	23.2	26.4
Modulus (GPa)	76.1	67.3	65.6
Strength(MPa)	800	653	651
Achievement ratio(%)	88.7	81	77.1

3.3.3 Tensile test

The Vf, modulus and strength, achievement ratio are shown in Table II. Relationships between

achievement ratio and essential molding time are shown in Figure.6. The achievement ratio was linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area. The tensile strength was also linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area.

Figure 6. Relationships between the achievement ratio and essential molding time Relationships between tensile strength and essential molding time

4. Effect of viscosity

Even in the case of the condition with high thermal capacity, Impregnation time was not enough, and un-impregnation area was observed. The essential molding time was still shorter than impregnation time. This equation express the impregnation time. Impregnation time is proportional to the melted viscosity of the resin . So, Impregnation time was shorten by using a low viscosity resin.

4.1 Materials

Carbon fibers (UTS50-12000 F22 800tex, Toho Tenax) were used as the reinforcement while the PA66 resin fiber (L-56T96SLM Nylon66 56dtex, melting temperature: 265 °C) were used as the matrix resin. Viscosity of resin fiber is lower than other resin fiber. Carbon fibers (UTS50 12000 filaments) and PA66 (L-56T96SLM) were combined in a parallel hybrid yarn arrangement and used as the BYs and MEYs and CYs. Specification of tubular braided fabrics was designed on equal terms with second.

TABLE III. TYPE OF SPECIMENS

Sample name	No.4	No.5	No.6	No.7
Filling ratio (%)	100	110	120	110
Number of CYs	79	77	73	77
Vfi	49.2	44.7	40.9	44.7
Molding speed(mm/min)	22	22	22	50

4.2 Pultrusion system

The temperature at each sections of the molding die in case of low viscosity resin was set respectively at 275, 275, 275, 260, 255, 255 °C from the entrance side. Temperature history, cross-sectional observation and tensile test were performed.

4.3 Result and discussion

4.3.1 Temperature history

The thermal evolution inside the beam during pultrusion in low viscosity resin is shown in Figure 7. The essential molding time are shown in Table IV. Relationships between the essential molding time and filling ratio are shown in Figure 8. When the filling ratio was increased, the essential molding time decreased. As a result, the point that internal temperature of braided fabrics achieved molding temperature shifted away from the entrance to exit of molding, due to incomplete heating up inside the molding as in the case of high viscosity resin.

Figure7. Temperature history in low viscosity resin

Figure8. Relationships between the achievement ratio and essential molding time

4.3.2 Cross sectional observation

The cross sectional photographs of specimens in low viscosity resin are shown in Figure 9. In the case of high viscosity resin, the un-impregnation area increased with increasing the filling ratio (Figure.4). In the case of low viscosity resin, the un-impregnation area was not observed for all specimens. However, voids appear in the case of low viscosity. The un-impregnation areas of specimens are shown in TABLE IV. The void content was decreased with decreasing the essential molding time. It was considered that void was generated by the thermal degradation.

Figure9. Cross section of specimen in low viscosity resin

TABLE IV. TYPE OF SPECIMENS

Sample name	No.4	No.5	No.6	No.7	No.8
Essential Molding time(min)	4.74	4.49	4.18	Non	2.18
Void contents	17.8	16.4	15.1	14.9	12.5
Modulus(GPa)	76.5	74.9	73.2	72.9	73.5
Strength(MPa)	544	503	522	557	766
Achievement ratio(%)	89.9	89.7	89.4	87.3	89.7

4.3.3 Tensile test

The Vf, modulus and strength are shown in Table IV. The tensile strength was also linearly increased with increasing the essential molding time. Relationships between achievement ratio and essential molding time are shown in Figure10. The achievement ratio of modulus was linearly increased with increasing the molding time. Relationships between tensile strength and essential molding time are shown in Figure11. The tensile strength was linearly increased with increasing the essential molding time in the case of high viscosity. But the tensile strength with low viscosity resin was decrease, because void was generated by the thermal degradation.

Figure 10. Relationships between the achievement ratio and essential molding time

Figure 11. Relationships between the tensile strength and essential molding time

5. Effect of die temperature

This equation express the impregnation time. Impregnation time is proportional to the melted viscosity of the resin . So, Impregnation time was shorten by setting high die temperature as compared to condition on effect of filling ratio.

5.1 Materials

Carbon fibers (UTS50-12000 F22 800tex, Toho Tenax) were used as the reinforcement while the PA66 resin fiber (L-235T35B Nylon66 235dtex, melting temperature: 265 °C) were used as the matrix resin. Carbon fibers (UTS50 12000 filaments) and PA66 (L-235T35B) were combined in a parallel hybrid yarn arrangement and used as the BYs and MEYs and CYs. Specification of tubular braided fabrics was designed on equal terms with second.

TABLE V. TYPE OF SPECIMENS

Sample name	Filling ratio (%)	Number of CYs	Vfi	Molding speed(m m/min)
No.9,10,11,12	100	79	49.2	22

5.2 Pultrusion system

The temperature at each sections of the molding die is shown in Figure 12. The pultruded beam was pulled out by pulling system. The pulling system is composed of six motor driven rollers that compressed and pulled the pultruded beams. The pultruded beam was cooled by compressed air at the exit of molding die.

Figure 12. Setting temperature of molding die

5.3 Result and discussion

5.3.1 Temperature history

The thermal evolution inside the beam during pultrusion is shown in Figure 13. The essential molding time are shown in Table V. When the max die temperature was increased, the essential molding time increased.

Figure 13. Temperature history

5.3.2 Cross sectional observation

The cross sectional photographs of specimens in low viscosity resin are shown in Figure 14. In the case of high die temperature, the un-impregnation area decreased with increasing the essential molding time. The un-impregnation areas of specimens are shown in TABLE V. Relationships between un-impregnation area and molding time are shown Figure 5. The un-impregnation area decreased with increasing the essential molding time.

Figure14. Cross section of specimen in low viscosity resin

Figure15. Relationships between the un-impregnation area and essential molding time

TABLE V. TYPE OF SPECIMENS

Sample name	No.9	No.10	No.11	No.12
Essential Molding time(min)	4.74	4.49	4.18	Non
Void contents	17.8	16.4	15.1	14.9
Modulus(GPa)	76.5	74.9	73.2	72.9
Strength(MPa)	544	503	522	557
Achievement ratio(%)	89.9	89.7	89.4	87.3

5.3.3 Tensile test

The Vf, modulus and strength are shown in Table V. The tensile strength was also linearly increased with increasing the essential molding time. Relationships between achievement ratio and essential molding time are shown in Figure.16. The achievement ratio of modulus was linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area. Relationships between tensile strength and essential molding time are shown in Figure.16. The tensile strength was linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area.

Figure16. Relationships between the achievement ratio and essential molding time Relationships between tensile strength and essential molding time

6. CONCLUSION

The point that internal temperature of braided fabrics achieved molding temperature shifted away from the entrance to exit of molding, and pressure can be applied only at taper zone. As a result, the essential molding time was calculated. The effect of the essential molding time effects after molding on the molding state and the mechanical properties were investigated. It was concluded that the most important condition was the essential molding time. The essential molding time was decreased with increasing filling ratio. The un-impregnation area was decreased with increasing the essential molding time. The achievement ratio was linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area. The tensile strength was also linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area. It is clarified that design of filling ratio with 100% results in the highest thermal capacity and increasing essential molding time. The essential molding time can be increased by controlling the molding temperature, pultrusion speed and viscosity of resin. So, Impregnation time was shortened by using a low viscosity resin. The achievement ratio of modulus was linearly increased with increasing the molding time. The tensile strength was linearly increased with increasing the essential molding time in the case of high viscosity. But the tensile strength with low viscosity resin was decrease, because void was generated by the thermal degradation. In the next, Impregnation time was shortened by setting high die temperature as compared to condition on effect of filling ratio. When the max die temperature was increased, the essential molding time increased. In the case of high die temperature, the un-impregnation area decreased with increasing the essential molding time. The achievement ratio of modulus was linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area. The tensile strength was linearly increased with decreasing the un-impregnation area.